

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MASSAQUOI****FIRST NAME: JAMES CONRAD****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In research, when researchers collect information...

- They look for specific data to test and support an answer to a question their topic inspired them to ask¹**
- They engage and convince people to provide the information
- They collect and test various data to answer the question they are inspired to ask
- They do all of the above

2. Which does not fit the definition of plagiarism?

- Quoting a source without using quotation marks—even if you do cite it

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20.

- Submitting material that, in part or whole, is entirely one's own work but attributing those same portions to their correct source²**
- the uncredited use (both intentional and unintentional) of somebody else's words or ideas
- Quoting or paraphrasing material without citing the source of that material
3. Turabian style guide is the student version of the...
- The Harvard University Press
- The Chicago Manual of Style³**
- The American Psychological Association
- The WHO Rule of Style
4. In academic writing, it is advisable to do the following if a writer is not sure of which citation style to use
- Use the citation style appropriate to their particular field once familiar with the style
- Comply with the institution's requirements for academic writing
- Use a style that is convenient for the writer
- Consult your instructor⁴**
5. Reasons for citing your work may not include...
- To give credit to the source - researcher/writers

² Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 221.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 13.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 141.

- To show readers that you understand academic writing⁵**
- To reassure readers about the accuracy of your facts
- To show readers the research tradition that informs your work
6. With a few exceptions, WHO spellings for diseases and other medical terms follow the...
- British usage⁶**
- North American Usage
- Both
- None
7. In doing a systematic identification, location and analysis of materials related to the research problem, the researcher does a...
- Critical analysis
- Literature Review⁷**
- Summative description
- Descriptive analysis
8. When a researcher evaluates the usefulness of sources for relevance, they do the following, except...

⁵ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 140.

⁶ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (World Health Organization, 2013), 13.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 352.

- Skim page by page in paragraphs in chapters, then the first and last paragraphs that use a lot of keywords
 - Skim its index for your keywords, then skim the pages on which those words occur⁸**
 - Skim the first and last paragraphs in chapters that use a lot of your keywords
 - Skim page by page in paragraphs in chapters that use a lot of your keywords
9. A qualitative research methodology that is based on a descriptive and inductive approach to data collection is
- Critical Incident⁹**
 - Survey
 - Document Review
 - Online data collection
10. Academic or scholarly writing must produce quality writing that is...
- Clear, concise, and explicit
 - Clear, concise, precise, and bold¹⁰**
 - Clear, succinct, precise and to the point
 - Clear, concise, precise and interesting

⁸ Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 41.

⁹ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 458.

¹⁰Ibid., 212.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th Ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations; Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. Fitzgerald. 9th ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Second ed. World Health Organization, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.